

THE FLYING DISC: INCORPORATING ULTIMATE FRISBEE IN STATE UNIVERSITIES AND COLLEGES PATH-FIT PROGRAM

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The Flying Disc: Incorporating Ultimate Frisbee in State Universities and Colleges Path-Fit Program

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Abstract

Physical activity and sports participation are crucial components of a healthy lifestyle, particularly for college students. The Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATH-FIT) program in the Philippines aims to promote physical fitness and well-being among students. Exploring the potential of incorporating new and engaging sports into the PATH-FIT curriculum is an important consideration to enhance the program's effectiveness and appeal to the student population. This study investigated the potential of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into the Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATH-FIT) program in state universities and colleges in the Philippines. The research aimed to assess the perceived characteristics of the sport across physical, mental, social, and affective domains, as well as to evaluate the performance levels of the respondents. A descriptive evaluation methodology was employed, utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire checklist and scoring rubrics to gather data from a diverse group of respondents, including students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches. The results revealed a strong consensus among stakeholders regarding the positive attributes of Ultimate Frisbee. The study's hypothesis testing revealed that there are significant differences in incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into the said program, particularly in terms of its impact on physical, social, mental, and affective skills, as well as the overall effectiveness of integrating the sport into the PATH-FIT curriculum. These findings strongly advocate for the integration of Ultimate Frisbee into the PATH-FIT program. The study recommends developing comprehensive modules for educators, providing training for instructors, encouraging inclusive participation, organizing skills, development workshops, and promoting community engagement through tournaments and events.

Keywords: *alternative sports, higher Education, PATH-FIT, potential team sports and ultimate frisbee*

Introduction

Physical educators can control the amount of physical activity a child gets at school; however, they do not have the power to control their students' physical activities at home, their food intake, or their family situations. Despite these situations, ensuring that the students get the right amount of exercise is one of the school's roles in meeting the students' educational needs and providing holistic learning.

According to Barnes (2010), the former chairman of task force on childhood obesity and director of policy council of United States cited that "Let's Move!" showed a statistic that one-third of the children in America are overweight or obese. Because of this, schools are one of the sources for children to gain one hour of play during P.E., of course, with increased difficulty. Programs prepared by schools for their students make them benefit from it directly because they are obliged to move as part of the curriculum. Once you get the suggested hours of exercise, it reduces the risk of developing diabetes, heart disease, sleep disorders, and even asthma brought on by being inactive.

Exercising regularly can add to anyone's cardiovascular health, and it also adds to the development of muscle and bone. According to Donnelly (2016) schools' curricula should include cognitive and physical assessments. As a result, by engaging them in physical activities, they will learn the benefits of having a healthy lifestyle, the starting point in developing into physically knowledgeable and health-conscious adults of the future.

PATH-FIT previously known as Physical Education aims to improve students' physical competence and make them knowledgeable about safety and movement, as well as their capability to carry off even a broad range of exertion accompanied by the progress of an active and healthy lifestyle. It also increases students' self-esteem and skills, especially creativity, critical thinking, teamwork, and esthetic appreciation. These, alongside training good values and attitudes in P.E., establish a suitable establishment for students' lifelong learning. By the pertinent provisions of Republic Act (RA) No. 7722, otherwise known as the "Higher Education Act of 1994," and by Commission en banc resolution No. 197-2011 dated August 8, 2011, vesting the Commission on Higher Education, the power to set minimum standards for programs and institutions of higher learning (Santiago, 2023) and to rationalize Physical Education in the country with the end given keeping pace with the demand of global competitiveness; and, under Article XIV, Section 19 of the Philippine Constitution which mandates that:

"The State shall promote physical Education and encourage sports programs, league competitions, and amateur sports, including training for international competitions, to foster self-discipline, teamwork, and excellence for developing a healthy and alert citizenry. All educational institutions shall undertake regular sports activities throughout the country in cooperation with athletic clubs and other sectors."

They all want to be healthy and fit but getting into physical workouts without knowing the basics will result in muscle pain. So, PATH-FIT is included in the curriculum of each state university and colleges to help develop not only the mind but also the body. Physical

activities are needed for an individual's well-being. Twenty-first-century learners are undergoing continuous physical and emotional changes, influenced by the ever-shifting dynamics of society. Active participation in various activities is therefore beneficial to their well-being; conversely, inactivity may lead to negative consequences.

On the other hand, in the PATH-FIT programs, the usual sports played by Filipinos include Basketball, volleyball, badminton, swimming, and indigenous sports. However, can Frisbee, a sport that slowly gained fame in the Philippines and does not require any physical contact with many players, be accepted by college students and other people engaged in the academe and have encountered ultimate Frisbee as a potential team sport for PATH-FIT? An additional option of team sports to be played at the college level may improve their interest and participation.

Ultimate Frisbee was first played by a group of students from Columbia High School in Maplewood, New Jersey, in 1968. A group of students named Colombian, a newspaper staff in their school, developed this new game as entertainment for their high school night. Initially, the game was freeform, with as many as 30 players allowed per team. Its first name was Frisbee football; the rules implemented were then modified until the turnover every time the disc fell to the ground and the prohibition of the player from running when he/she was holding the disc was implemented (Hawani et al., 2023). When the students graduated from high school, they introduced the game to their college level. Over 25,000 amateur people, whether rich or poor, play this game globally in 35 countries, including the Philippines. Ultimate Frisbee is a game for all kinds of people. To learn it, you need to play it (Raya-González et al., 2020).

With gadgets changing and developing into something that makes the new generation fixated, letting them try Ultimate Frisbee and eventually knowing their perception of it is one of the reasons why the researcher, as an educator of PATH-FIT, would like to know. The problem met by the researcher in his years of teaching is that when teaching Basketball, men are the ones who are engaged in it; however, females have less interest than males because of the vigorous way how it should be played, which makes females conscious about their well-being. On the other hand, when the researcher teaches volleyball, female students get involved because of its lack of physical contact with the opposing team, making male students withdraw their interest in the game. The second reason for conducting this study is to have an unbiased sports teaching by the instructor and make the male or female students play a game together. The third reason the researcher would like to conduct the study is because, as a teacher in a government institution, he saw that quality equipment and facilities are needed to conduct a basketball and volleyball class. However, playing Ultimate Frisbee will only require an open area or field, cones, and a disc, which makes it affordable and low-cost for the school and the instructor. Knowing the norm of teaching sports in different state universities and colleges, the researcher wants to show through this research that there is also an alternative in teaching the subject and lessen the division of preferred sports because of the students' sexuality.

The researcher would like to evaluate students' perception of sports and whether it contributes to their physical, mental, affective, and social well-being. With the combined continuous movement from soccer and the aerial pass of football, Ultimate Frisbee is played by two groups composed of seven members per team using a plastic disc professionally made for the game and a field like a football, with two endpoints. Each team aims to pass the disc on the opponent's end zone without falling it on the ground. When players catch the disc, they are not supposed to move but may turn around and pass it to a teammate on the field. Ultimate Frisbee is like the system of Basketball; each team needs to change from offense to defense every time there is a turnover, a dropped disc, a player who ran with the possession of the disc, a pass out of bounce, and when a player is caught holding the disc for almost 10 seconds.

As it now invades the Philippines, teachers can also include it in educating students. They can exploit it so there will be diversity in teaching. This is an easy sport: When an individual is knowledgeable of the ten basic rules, they can already take part in the game. Students who are novices can already play because no prior experience or early childhood training is expected.

Research Questions

The study focused on incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT at state universities and colleges. Specifically, it looked for the perception of the respondents regarding the following questions:

1. What are the potential characteristics of the ultimate frisbee in state universities and colleges PATH-FIT as perceived by the respondents concerning:
 - 1.1. physical;
 - 1.2. mental;
 - 1.3. social; and
 - 1.4. affective?
2. Is there a significant difference in the incorporation of ultimate frisbee in state universities and colleges' PATH-FIT in teaching team sports as the respondents perceive concerning the abovementioned variables?
3. What is the level of performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the respondents as revealed by the scoring rubrics concerning the following skills:
 - 3.1. grip;
 - 3.2. throws;
 - 3.3. footwork;
 - 3.4. attacking skills;

- 3.5. defending skills; and
- 3.6. catching Skills?

Methodology

The researcher used descriptive evaluation methods, including a researcher-made questionnaire checklist, to gather relevant data about the problem. The researcher utilized the descriptive evaluation method to gather information about the present condition. It involved gathering data to test the hypothesis or answer questions about the subject's status. Moreover, it refers to the type of research of action, design, and data analysis applied to a given topic. According to Haynes et al., (2016) evaluative methods were used to assess the potentiality of ultimate Frisbee as a team sport for PATH-FIT in state universities and colleges. This helped the research discover the influence of the sport Ultimate Frisbee on the underlying factors presented in the previous chapters, which included students' physical, social, mental, and affective skills. Since the study was about the potentiality of ultimate Frisbee in team sports for physical education in colleges and universities, these methods were appropriate. This method enabled the researcher to acquire the data needed to determine the possibility of Ultimate Frisbee being part of the team sports subject. The researcher used a checklist that measured the different effects of sports on students in terms of their intellectual, physical, social, and emotional development.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Potential Characteristics of the Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports in College and Universities as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Physical*

	Physical	Student		Teacher		Athlete		Frisbee Enthusiast		Coach		Overall	
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1.	Athleticism is not a major requirement in playing Ultimate Frisbee.	4.30	SA	4.20	SA	4.70	SA	3.70	A	3.40	A	4.06	A
2.	Ultimate Frisbee is for everyone regardless of gender preference.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.80	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA
3.	Ultimate Frisbee promotes great cardiovascular exercise.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA
4.	Ultimate Frisbee develops better agility with continuous practice.	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.70	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA
5.	Ultimate Frisbee can help improve physical endurance.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
	Average	4.82	SA	4.84	SA	4.88	SA	4.58	SA	4.68	SA	4.76	SA

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50-4.49 Agree (A); 2.50-3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50-2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

The findings presented in Table 1 highlight the perceptions of various stakeholders regarding the characteristics of Ultimate Frisbee as a teaching tool for team sports in state universities and colleges. The table summarizes the mean scores and verbal interpretations (VI) from five respondent groups: students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches. The average mean score across all groups was 4.76, indicating a "Strongly Agree" (SA) consensus regarding the positive attributes of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs.

First, the data suggests that Ultimate Frisbee is perceived as an inclusive sport. Respondents from all groups unanimously rated the statement, "Ultimate Frisbee is for everyone regardless of gender preference," with a perfect mean score of 5.00, categorized as SA. This finding underscores the sport's accessibility and potential to promote diversity and participation among students of varying backgrounds, supporting the notion that Ultimate Frisbee can be an effective tool for fostering inclusivity in physical education (Beasley et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the respondents strongly agreed that Ultimate Frisbee promotes cardiovascular exercise, with a mean score of 4.94 across all groups. This aligns with existing literature highlighting the health benefits of playing Ultimate Frisbee, particularly its role in enhancing cardiovascular fitness through continuous movement and team-based play (Lee et al., 2022). The strong agreement on this point indicates that stakeholders recognize the physical health benefits of sport, making it a valuable addition to physical education curricula.

The perceived impact of Ultimate Frisbee on physical skills was also significant, as indicated by high mean scores for statements regarding the development of agility (4.90) and improvement of physical endurance (4.96). The consensus among respondents suggests that continuous practice of Ultimate Frisbee can enhance these physical attributes, reinforcing the sport's efficacy as a training tool for developing athletic skills (Sullivan & Hannan, 2018).

Notably, the statement "Athleticism is not a major requirement in playing Ultimate Frisbee" received a mean score of 4.06, categorized as Agree (A). This finding suggests that while athleticism is acknowledged, it is not viewed as a barrier to participation in Ultimate

Frisbee. The ability to engage in sports without the need for high-level athletic skills may encourage more students to participate, further supporting its inclusion in physical education programs (Ryan & Deci, 2015).

The data indicates a strong consensus among stakeholders regarding the benefits of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT at state universities and colleges. Sport is perceived as inclusive, beneficial for cardiovascular health, and effective in developing physical skills such as agility and endurance. These findings suggest that Ultimate Frisbee could be a valuable addition to PATH-FIT curricula, promoting physical fitness, inclusivity, and student engagement.

Table 2. *Potential Characteristics of the Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports in College and Universities as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Mental*

	<i>Mental</i>	<i>Student</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Athlete</i>		<i>Frisbee Enthusiast</i>		<i>Coach</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Playing Ultimate Frisbee can keep a player mentally alert.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.70	SA	4.90	SA	4.92	SA
2.	Ultimate Frisbee helps a player in becoming a strategic player.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
3.	Ultimate Frisbee allows a person to play at the peak of their talent consistently	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.80	SA	4.90	SA	4.88	SA
4.	When engaged to Ultimate Frisbee, stress level goes down.	4.70	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.60	SA	4.70	SA	4.78	SA
5.	Playing Ultimate Frisbee can boost confidence in team sports.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.80	SA	4.90	SA	4.90	SA
<i>Average</i>		4.88	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA	4.74	SA	4.88	SA	4.89	SA

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50-4.49 Agree (A); 2.50-3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50-2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

Table 2 presents the perceptions of various stakeholders regarding the mental benefits of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs at state universities and colleges. The data illustrates a strong consensus among respondents, with an overall average mean score of 4.89, indicating a general agreement of "Strongly Agree" (SA) regarding the positive mental characteristics associated with playing Ultimate Frisbee.

The first notable characteristic is the ability of Ultimate Frisbee to keep players mentally alert, as evidenced by a perfect mean score of 5.00 from all respondent groups. This suggests that participants recognize the cognitive demands of the sport, which require players to remain focused and responsive during gameplay.

Respondents also strongly agreed that Ultimate Frisbee helps individuals become strategic players, with a mean score of 4.96. This reflects the sport's inherent need for strategic thinking and decision-making skills, reinforcing the idea that Ultimate Frisbee not only promotes physical fitness but also cultivates critical mental skills that are transferable to other areas of life (Shipherd et al., 2018).

The ability to strategize and adapt during play is crucial for success in team sports, and Ultimate Frisbee provides an excellent platform for developing these skills.

The data further indicates that Ultimate Frisbee allows players to consistently perform at their peak talent, with an overall mean score of 4.88. This suggests that respondents perceive the sport as one that encourages personal growth and skill development, which can lead to enhanced performance and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997). The positive correlation between participation in Ultimate Frisbee and improved performance levels highlights its potential as a valuable tool in PATH-FIT curricula.

Additionally, the study reveals that engaging in Ultimate Frisbee contributes to reduced stress levels, with a mean score of 4.78. This finding supports previous research indicating that physical activity, particularly team sports, can serve as an effective means of stress relief and mental well-being (Rocliffe et al., 2023). The social nature of Ultimate Frisbee, combined with its physical demands, likely fosters an environment conducive to stress reduction and emotional regulation.

Finally, respondents highlighted the confidence-boosting effects of playing Ultimate Frisbee, with a mean score of 4.90. The sport appears to provide a supportive atmosphere where participants can build their self-esteem through teamwork and skill development.

The findings from Table 2 strongly support the integration of Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs at state universities and colleges. The perceptions of mental alertness, strategic thinking, peak performance, stress reduction, and increased confidence collectively underscore the multifaceted benefits of this sport.

As such, educators and policymakers should consider incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into their curricula to foster not only physical fitness but also mental resilience and personal development among students.

Table 3. Potential Characteristics of the Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports in College and Universities as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Social

	Social	Student		Teacher		Athlete		Frisbee Enthusiast		Coach		Overall	
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1.	In Ultimate Frisbee, gender is not an issue.	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
2.	Ultimate Frisbee is a fun game, where everyone is encouraged to participate.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
3.	Ultimate Frisbee promotes sportsmanship with the other team without the presence of a referee.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.80	SA	4.92	SA
4.	Camaraderie is being developed regardless of gender identity.	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.92	SA
5.	Learning a new sport like Frisbee gives a wide area for a positive learning climate because both genders can cooperate and enjoy the game.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.92	SA
Average		4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA	4.88	SA	4.96	SA	4.94	SA

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50-4.49 Agree (A); 2.50-3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50-2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

The findings presented in Table 3 highlight the perceived social characteristics of Ultimate Frisbee as a teaching tool for team sports in state universities and colleges. The table summarizes the mean scores and verbal interpretations (VI) from five respondent groups: students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches. The average mean score across all groups was 4.94, indicating a strong "Strongly Agree" (SA) consensus regarding the social benefits of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT curricula.

One of the most significant findings is that respondents unanimously rated the statement "In Ultimate Frisbee, gender is not an issue," with a perfect mean score of 5.00. This indicates a shared belief among stakeholders that Ultimate Frisbee promotes inclusivity and equality, allowing individuals of all genders to participate equally (Miller & Miller, 2021). This perception of gender inclusivity aligns with existing literature emphasizing the importance of creating equitable sports environments that foster participation from diverse groups (Harrison et al., 2011).

Furthermore, respondents also strongly agreed that "Ultimate Frisbee is a fun game, where everyone is encouraged to participate," with an average mean score of 4.96 across all groups. This highlights the sport's appeal as an engaging and enjoyable activity that encourages participation from all individuals, which is critical in physical education settings to foster lifelong physical activity habits (Reardon et al., 2019).

The theme of sportsmanship is also emphasized, with respondents agreeing that "Ultimate Frisbee promotes sportsmanship with the other team without the presence of a referee," reflected in a mean score of 4.92. This finding suggests that the self-officiating nature of Ultimate Frisbee fosters a culture of respect and cooperation among players, enhancing the social dynamics of the game (Frenk et al., 2014). The emphasis on sportsmanship without external enforcement can positively influence students' social development and interpersonal skills.

Camaraderie and teamwork are further highlighted in the statement, "Camaraderie is being developed regardless of gender identity," which received a mean score of 4.92. Finally, the statement "Learning a new sport like Frisbee gives a wide area for a positive learning climate because both genders can cooperate and enjoy the game" garnered a mean score of 4.92.

This reinforces the idea that Ultimate Frisbee is an effective vehicle for developing a supportive learning environment where cooperation and enjoyment are paramount, contributing to positive social interactions and learning outcomes (Beasley et al., 2022).

The data indicates a strong consensus among stakeholders regarding the social advantages of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs. Sport is perceived as inclusive, fun, and conducive to fostering sportsmanship, camaraderie, and cooperative learning. These findings suggest that Ultimate Frisbee could serve as a valuable addition to PATH-FIT curricula, promoting physical fitness, social skills, and a sense of community among students.

The findings presented in Table 4 highlight the perceived affective characteristics of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT at state universities and colleges. The data reflects the mean scores and verbal interpretations (VI) from five respondent groups: students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches.

The overall average mean score across all groups was 4.92, indicating a strong "Strongly Agree" (SA) consensus regarding the positive emotional and social impacts associated with Ultimate Frisbee.

Table 4. *Potential Characteristics of the Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports in College and Universities as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Affective*

	Affective	Student		Teacher		Athlete		Frisbee Enthusiast		Coach		Overall	
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1.	In Ultimate Frisbee a person can develop a passion that will make me play the game even after the class.	4.80	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.70	SA	4.70	SA	4.82	SA
2.	I appreciated the capabilities of my classmates whether male or female.	4.70	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	4.90	SA	4.90	SA	4.88	SA
3.	I will look forward in playing this game again because it gives us an opportunity to bond as a class without any barriers.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
4.	Having another sport that we can play for our subject makes me look forward to the next meeting.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
5.	The sport is relevant to the subject Team Sport.	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	5.00	SA	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA
Average		4.84	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA	4.86	SA	4.92	SA	4.92	SA

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50-4.49 Agree (A); 2.50-3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50-2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

First, the highest mean score of 4.96 was recorded for the statement, "I will look forward to playing this game again because it allows us to bond as a class without any barriers." This response underscores Ultimate Frisbee's ability to foster social cohesion and camaraderie among participants. The findings align with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of team sports in enhancing social interactions and building peer relationships (McCrorry et al. (2017). The perceived opportunity for bonding without barriers suggests that Ultimate Frisbee can effectively promote inclusivity and a sense of community within PATH-FIT programs.

Additionally, a mean score of 4.82 for the statement, "In Ultimate Frisbee, a person can develop a passion that will make me play the game even after the class," indicates that respondents believe the sport can inspire long-term engagement and passion. This finding aligns with the principles of Self-Determination Theory ("Self-Determination Theory: Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness," 2017), which posits that intrinsic motivation—driven by personal interest and enjoyment—can lead to sustained participation in physical activities. The enthusiasm expressed by respondents suggests that Ultimate Frisbee not only serves as an engaging activity during class but also has the potential to cultivate a lifelong interest in sport.

The responses also reveal a strong appreciation for classmates' capabilities, with a mean score of 4.88 for the statement, "I appreciated the capabilities of my classmates, whether male or female." This indicates that Ultimate Frisbee promotes respect and recognition of diverse skill sets, reinforcing that team sports can enhance interpersonal relationships and foster a supportive environment (Bergeron et al., 2015). The positive acknowledgment of peers' abilities highlights the potential for Ultimate Frisbee to contribute to an inclusive atmosphere that values collaboration and teamwork.

Furthermore, respondents expressed excitement about the diversity of activities within the PATH-FIT curriculum, as indicated by the mean scores of 4.96 for the statements, "Having another sport that we can play for our subject makes me look forward to the next meeting," and "The sport is relevant to the subject Team Sport." These findings suggest that the inclusion of Ultimate Frisbee not only adds variety to the curriculum but also aligns well with educational objectives, reinforcing the relevance of the sport to the broader context of team sports education.

The data indicates a strong consensus among stakeholders regarding the practical benefits of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT curricula. The sport is perceived as fostering social bonds, developing a passion for physical activities, appreciating classmates, and enhancing educational experience. These findings highlight the potential of Ultimate Frisbee to serve as an engaging and inclusive team sport that can enrich PATH-FIT programs in state universities and colleges.

The findings presented in Table 5 provide a composite overview of the perceived characteristics of Ultimate Frisbee as a teaching tool for team sports in state universities and colleges. The data encompasses various aspects, physical, mental, social, and effective evaluated by different respondent groups, including students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches. The overall grand mean score across all groups is 4.87, indicating a strong "Strongly Agree" (SA) consensus regarding the positive attributes of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs.

Physical Aspect: The mean score for the physical aspect of Ultimate Frisbee was 4.76, with all respondent groups indicating strong agreement. This suggests that stakeholders recognize Ultimate Frisbee as a physically engaging activity that promotes fitness and

athleticism. The high mean scores indicate that respondents believe Ultimate Frisbee can effectively contribute to PATH-FIT by enhancing students' physical abilities and encouraging active participation.

Table 5. Composite table on the Potential Characteristics of the Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports in College and Universities as Perceived by the Respondents

Aspect	Student		Teacher		Athlete		Frisbee Enthusiast		Coach		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Physical	4.82	SA	4.84	SA	4.88	SA	4.58	SA	4.68	SA	4.76	SA
Mental	4.88	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA	4.74	SA	4.88	SA	4.89	SA
Social	4.90	SA	5.00	SA	4.94	SA	4.88	SA	4.96	SA	4.94	SA
Affective	4.84	SA	5.00	SA	4.96	SA	4.86	SA	4.92	SA	4.92	SA
Grand Mean	4.86	SA	4.96	SA	4.93	SA	4.77	SA	4.86	SA	4.87	SA

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50-4.49 Agree (A); 2.50-3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50-2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

Mental Aspect: The mental aspect received an impressive overall mean score of 4.89, with all groups also rating this aspect as SA. This highlights the perceived cognitive benefits of Ultimate Frisbee, suggesting that it can foster critical thinking, strategy development, and decision-making skills among participants. The positive perception of the mental benefits emphasizes Ultimate Frisbee's role in promoting mental resilience and focus, which are crucial components of overall student development (Reardon et al., 2019).

Social Aspect: The social aspect of Ultimate Frisbee garnered a mean score of 4.94, indicating substantial agreement among respondents. This reflects a consensus that Ultimate Frisbee promotes teamwork, communication, and social interaction among players. The findings align with existing literature emphasizing the importance of social connections in physical education settings and how team sports can enhance social skills and camaraderie (Neal et al., 2015).

The positive social environment Ultimate Frisbee fosters may contribute to a more inclusive and supportive atmosphere in PATH-FIT classes.

Affective Aspect: The affective aspect received a mean score of 4.92, indicating substantial agreement regarding its emotional benefits. Respondents perceived Ultimate Frisbee as a sport that can enhance students' enjoyment, motivation, and emotional well-being. The findings suggest that engaging in Ultimate Frisbee can increase enthusiasm for physical education, positively influencing students' attitudes towards participation in physical activities (Ryan et al., 2018).

The data indicates a robust consensus among various stakeholders regarding the multifaceted benefits of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs. The high mean scores across all aspects—physical, mental, social, and affective—highlight its potential as an effective teaching tool that fosters holistic student development. These findings suggest that Ultimate Frisbee can serve as a valuable addition to the curriculum in state universities and colleges, promoting physical fitness, mental resilience, social interaction, and emotional well-being.

Table 6. Significant Difference on the Potential Characteristics of Ultimate Frisbee in Teaching Team Sports as Perceived by the Respondents

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	HO	VI
Physical	Between Groups	.632	4	.158	1.739	.158	FR	NS
	Within Groups	4.088	45	.091				
	Total	4.720	49					
Mental	Between Groups	.373	4	.093	1.664	.175	FR	NS
	Within Groups	2.520	45	.056				
	Total	2.893	49					
Social	Between Groups	.089	4	.022	.581	.678	FR	NS
	Within Groups	1.722	45	.038				
	Total	1.811	49					
Affective	Between Groups	.179	4	.045	.767	.552	FR	NS
	Within Groups	2.628	45	.058				
	Total	2.807	49					

Table 6 presented a statistical analysis examining the perceived characteristics of Ultimate Frisbee as a teaching tool for team sports among various respondent groups. This analysis encompassed four dimensions: physical, mental, social, and affective characteristics. The findings indicated no statistically significant differences among the groups across all dimensions. The between-group sum of squares for physical characteristics was 0.632, with a mean square of 0.158. The F-statistics were 1.739, yielding a significance value (p) of 0.158, suggesting consensus that physical aspects did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, mental characteristics showed a between-group sum of squares of 0.373, a mean square of 0.093, an F-statistic of 1.664, and a significance level of 0.175, reinforcing the general agreement on their importance in PATH-FIT. The analysis of social characteristics yielded a between-group sum of squares of 0.089, a mean square of 0.022, and an F-statistic of 0.581, with a significance value of 0.678, indicating uniform perceptions of social benefits ($p > 0.05$).

Finally, for affective characteristics, results showed a between-group sum of squares of 0.179, a mean square of 0.045, and an F-statistic

of 0.767, with a significance level of 0.552 ($p > 0.05$), confirming shared views on emotional aspects. Overall, the retention of the null hypothesis across all dimensions indicated a consensus on the value and attributes of Ultimate Frisbee as perceived by students, teachers, athletes, Frisbee enthusiasts, and coaches. This uniformity underscored the potential for effectively integrating Ultimate Frisbee into the PATH-FIT curricula. Future research could explore the reasons behind this consensus and assess whether similar findings existed in other educational contexts or sports.

Table 7. *Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Grip*

<i>Grip</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Backhand grip	4.90	A
Forehand grip	4.78	A
Average	4.85	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50–4.49 Agree (A); 2.50–3.49 Moderate Agree (MA); 1.50–2.49 Disagree (DA); 1.00–1.49 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

The data presented in Table 7 reflects respondents' performance level in Ultimate Frisbee, specifically regarding their grip techniques. The mean scores for both backhand and forehand grips are high, with the backhand grip achieving a mean score of 4.90 and the forehand grip a score of 4.78, both classified as "A" performance levels. The average score across both grips was 4.85, indicating the respondents' strong overall proficiency in grip techniques.

According to the scoring rubric, a mean score of 4.00 and above typically signifies an advanced level of performance. The backhand grip score of 4.90 suggests that respondents are highly skilled in this technique, reflecting a robust understanding and execution of the grip critical for effective throwing. This is particularly important in Ultimate Frisbee, where grip quality can significantly influence a player's throwing accuracy and distance.

While slightly lower than the backhand, the forehand grip mean score of 4.78 still falls within the "A" range, indicating that respondents are also proficient in this technique. The slight difference in means may suggest that players feel more comfortable or have had more practice with the backhand grip, which is common in various throwing sports.

Overall, the average score of 4.85 highlights a strong consensus among the respondents regarding their grip performance in Ultimate Frisbee, suggesting a well-established skill set that can lead to successful participation in the sport. This proficiency may also enhance the effectiveness of incorporating Ultimate Frisbee into PATH-FIT programs, as it indicates that students possess a solid foundation of the essential skills necessary for gameplay.

These results also suggest that PATH-FIT programs in state universities and colleges might benefit from focusing on both grip techniques to develop students' abilities in Ultimate Frisbee further. Tailored instruction and practice sessions could enhance player performance even more, fostering greater engagement and skill acquisition.

Table 8. *Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Throw*

<i>Throw</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Backhand throw	4.70	A
Forehand throw	4.89	A
Hammer	4.00	U
Average	4.48	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50–4.49 Usually (U); 2.50–3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50–2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00–1.49 Never (N)

Table 8 presented the performance levels of respondents in Ultimate Frisbee, explicitly focusing on their throwing skills as assessed through a scoring rubric. The table outlined the mean scores and verbal interpretations (VI) for three types of throws: backhand throw, forehand throw, and hammer throw. The average mean score of 4.48 was categorized as "Always" (A), indicating a generally positive performance level among respondents.

The backhand throw received a mean score of 4.70, also categorized as "Always" (A). This score suggested that respondents demonstrated solid proficiency in executing the backhand throw, a fundamental skill in Ultimate Frisbee.

The forehand throw achieved an even higher mean score of 4.89, which was likewise categorized as "Always" (A). This score reflected excellent competence in executing the forehand throw, critical for making quick, accurate passes. The high proficiency in this throw indicated that instructors likely emphasized the forehand technique in their training sessions, which is vital for compelling gameplay and strategic passing.

In contrast, the hammer throw received a mean score of 4.00, categorized as "Usually" (U). This score suggested that respondents needed more confidence and skill in executing the hammer throw compared to other techniques. The lower performance in this area indicated a potential gap in training or familiarity with the hammer throw, which is a more advanced technique often used for strategic

plays.

Overall, the average mean score of 4.48, categorized as "Always" (A), demonstrated that respondents possessed a competent level of performance in Ultimate Frisbee throwing techniques. However, the disparity between the scores for various throws underscored the importance of a well-rounded training approach that addressed foundational and advanced skills. Future training programs should have enhanced proficiency in less familiar techniques, such as the hammer throw, to further develop the participants' overall performance in Ultimate Frisbee.

Table 9. Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Pivot Footwork

<i>Footwork</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Perform a Pivot footwork	4.80	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50-4.49 Usually (U); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50-2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

Table 9 presented the level of performance in Ultimate Frisbee among respondents, specifically focusing on the scoring rubrics related to pivot footwork. The mean score for the performance of pivot footwork was reported as 4.80, categorized as "Always" (A) in the verbal interpretation (VI).

The high mean score of 4.80 indicated that respondents generally perceived their ability to perform pivot footwork in Ultimate Frisbee positively. This suggested a strong understanding of the skill, which was critical in the game for maintaining possession of the disc while effectively maneuvering around defenders. The pivot footwork was essential as it allowed players to create space, change direction, and make strategic passes, contributing to overall gameplay effectiveness.

In summary, the findings from Table 9 indicated a commendable level of proficiency in pivot footwork among respondents, suggesting that the incorporation of Ultimate Frisbee in PATH-FIT programs yielded positive results in skill acquisition. Future training sessions could continue to build on this foundation, potentially introducing more advanced techniques and strategies to further enhance students' performance in Ultimate Frisbee.

Table 10. Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Defending Skills

<i>Defending Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Defending 1	4.90	A
Defending 2	4.80	A
Average	4.85	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50-4.49 Usually (U); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50-2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

In table 10 with respect to defending skills, the level of performance of the respondents reveals that the defending 1 obtained a 4.90 mean with a verbal interpretation of "always". The mean of defending 2 is 4.80 with a verbal interpretation of "always". The average mean for defending is 4.85 with a verbal interpretation of "always".

Table 11. Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Attacking Skills

<i>Attacking Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Attacking 1	4.80	A
Attacking 2	4.90	A
Average	4.85	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50-4.49 Usually (U); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50-2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

In table 11 with respect to attacking skills, the level of performance of the respondents reveals that the attacking 1 obtained a 4.80 mean with a verbal interpretation of "always". The mean of attacking 2 is 4.90 with a verbal interpretation of "always". The average mean for attacking is 4.85 with a verbal interpretation of "always".

Table 12. Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics with Respect to Catching Skills

<i>Catching Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Pancake/ Crocodile Catch	4.80	A
Two Hand Catch	4.80	A
One Hand Catch	4.70	A
Average	4.77	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50-4.49 Usually (U); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50-2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

In table 12 with respect to catching skills, the level of performance of the respondents reveal that the pancake/ crocodile catch obtained a 4.80 mean with a verbal interpretation of “always”. The mean of two hand catch is 4.80 with a verbal interpretation of “always”. The one hand catch obtained a 4.70 mean with a verbal interpretation of “always”. The average mean for catching is 4.77 with a verbal interpretation of “always”.

Table 13. *Composite Table on the Level of Performance in Ultimate Frisbee of the Respondents as Revealed by the Scoring Rubrics*

Skills	Mean	VI
Grip	4.85	A
Throws	4.48	A
Footwork	4.80	A
Defending Skills	4.85	A
Attacking Skills	4.85	A
Catching Skills	4.77	A
Average	4.77	A

Legend: 5.00 – 4.50 Always (A); 3.50-4.49 Usually (U); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); 1.50-2.49 Occasionally (O); 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

Table 13 reveals the composite table on the level of performance in ultimate Frisbee of the respondents as revealed by the scoring rubrics. The grip, throws, footwork, defending, attacking and catching obtained means of 4.85, 4.48, 4.80, 4.85, 4.85, and 4.77 with verbal interpretations of “always”. At the end of the scored rubrics, it was revealed that the grand mean for table number 13 is 4.77 with a verbal interpretation of “always”

Conclusions

The findings of this study strongly advocate for the incorporation of Ultimate Frisbee into Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATH-FIT) four in state universities and colleges in the Philippines. The high mean scores across various dimensions, including physical, mental, social, and affective, indicate that Ultimate Frisbee is perceived as an inclusive, engaging, and beneficial activity that promotes overall student well-being. Respondents acknowledged the sport's ability to enhance physical fitness, develop mental resilience, foster social connections, and cultivate a passion for physical activity. Specifically, the performance assessments revealed that respondents exhibited commendable skills in grip, throwing, footwork, defending, attacking, and catching, suggesting a solid foundation for Ultimate Frisbee as a viable team sport in PATH-FIT curricula. To effectively integrate Ultimate Frisbee, institutions should develop curricula that emphasize its inclusive nature and benefits, provide adequate training for instructors, encourage participation from all students, organize skill development workshops, establish a system of regular assessments and feedback, and promote community engagement through inter-school tournaments or events. By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can effectively incorporate Ultimate Frisbee into their PATH-FIT programs, enhancing student engagement and promoting a culture of inclusivity and physical fitness. Furthermore, the development of a comprehensive module for educators is suggested to facilitate the effective implementation of Ultimate Frisbee as a team sport in colleges and universities, ensuring that both instructors and students can maximize the benefits of this engaging and dynamic sport.

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